

Evaluation of the Effectiveness of Bio and Chemical Pesticides against the Cotton Thrips, *Thrips tabaci* L. under Laboratory Conditions

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Abstract:

The cotton thrips, *Thrips tabaci* L., a globally widespread pest, poses major challenges to vegetable crops, especially cucumber *Cucumis sativus* L., through direct feeding damage and disease transmission. This study evaluates the efficacy of two botanical biopesticides Tondexir 80% EC (red pepper and garlic extract) and Palizin 65% EC (organic saponins) and two chemical pesticides Super Hulk 11.8% EC (hexythiazox + abamectin) and Changer 24% SC (Chlorfenapyr) against *T. tabaci* under laboratory conditions. Thrips were collected from infested cucumber fields in Karbala Governorate, Iraq, and mortality rates were evaluated at different

concentrations (biopesticides: 1 ml and 2 ml; chemicals pesticides: 0.5 ml and 1 ml) and time periods (24, 48 and 72 h). The results showed that Super Hulk 11.8% EC achieved the highest efficacy, with 100% mortality within 48 and 72 h at both concentrations. Changer 24% SC showed moderate efficacy, with a maximum efficacy of 78.33% at 1 ml after 72 h. Among the biopesticides, Tondexir and Palizin showed significant mortality, with higher concentrations and prolonged exposure leading to improved outcomes. Palizin showed the highest mortality (83.33%) at 2 ml after 72 h. The study highlights the superior rapid action of chemical pesticides and the potential of bio pesticides as environmentally friendly alternatives. Integrated pest management strategies that combine these approaches are recommended to enhance efficacy, mitigate resistance development and reduce environmental impact. Further field studies are suggested to validate these findings.

Keywords: *Thrips tabaci*, Cucumber pest management, Tondexir, Palizin, Super Hulk, Changer.

Introduction

Vegetables are essential commodities, highly valued for their economic importance and as a major source of vital nutrients such as vitamins and minerals (Mahmood, 2018). Cucumber *Cucumis sativus* L., a cucurbit crop widely grown worldwide, is highly susceptible to insect infestations throughout its growing season (Ali & Saleh, 2020). Cucumber plant is usually infested with a various pest such as mites,

aphids, whiteflies, bugs, leafhoppers, mealybugs and thrips are phloem-feeding insects that attack a variety of crops. They cause significant damage to plants, either by directly feeding on sap or indirectly by transmitting diseases (Ahmed et al., 2020). The cotton thrips, *Thrips tabaci* L. (Thysanoptera: Thripidae), is a common pest of vegetable crops, and is distributed worldwide. Its range extends across tropical, subtropical and temperate climates (Roland et al., 1991). Thrips

feeding on immature cucumber fruits can cause significant damage, resulting in silvery scars and potential malformation of the fruit. This damage can significantly affect the quality and appearance, leading to lower -quality produce and reduce market value (Rosenheim et al.,1990).

The focus should now be not only on the use of different chemicals to control pests, but also on the use of biopesticides in minimum doses. This is important, as insect resistance to insecticides has been reported in many areas around the world (Salunkhe et al., 2020). Traditionally, chemical insecticides have been widely used to control thrips populations. However, the increasing development of insect resistance, coupled with concerns about environmental impact and human health, has led to a growing interest in alternative control measures (Barghout et al., 2022). Biopesticides, which are derived from natural sources such as plants, microorganisms or other biological agents, offer a promising solution as part of integrated pest management strategies. These alternatives are environmentally friendly and less likely to contribute to pest resistance (Njuguna et al., 2021).

The aim of the study is to evaluate the effectiveness of biopesticides, Tondexir 80% EC, Palizin 65%EC and chemical pesticides Super Hulk 11.8 % EC, Changer 24 % SC, against the cotton thrips., against the cotton thrips.

Material and Methods

Thrips specimens were collected from infested cucumber fields in various regions of Karbala province, brought to the laboratory, and identified based on morphological identification. Observations were made under stereomicroscope (LEICA MZ16) at 10X and 40X magnification at the Plant Protection Department, University of Kerbala. The main diagnostic characteristics, including the number of antennae segments, the presence of branched sensory cones, the coloration of antennae segments, the number of ocelli, the body color,

the arrangement of opercula on the forewings, and the features of the abdomen, were examined. The genus and species of thrips were determined using Pest Thrips of the World (Moritz et al., 2004).

The laboratory experiments were designed according to a completely randomized design (CRD). To establish a laboratory experiment, cucumber seeds of the Super Faris variety were planted in plastic pots with a diameter of 12 cm and a height of 12 cm. The pots contained a mixture of sterile clay soil and peat moss in a ratio of 1:1, with three seeds planted in each pot. The pots were placed in a well-lit area in the laboratory, where the temperature ranged between 25-30 °C and the relative humidity was 45-55%. Cucumber plants grown in pots in the laboratory were used to study the effect of direct spraying with plant extracts and insecticides on the life stages of cotton thrips when the number of leaves on the growing plants reached six leaves. Then, the leaves of cucumber plants infected with cotton thrips were collected from a greenhouse specially planted for this study at the College of Agriculture, Al-Hussainiya, Karbala. Pesticide application was carried out using a calibrated handheld compression sprayer (Kwazar) before application, and the pesticide was calibrated to spray each plate containing 10 replicates of adult thrips. Cucumber seedlings grown in plastic pots were sprayed two concentrations 1 and 2 ml / liter of Tondexir 80% EC and Palizin 65%EC (Table 1) at five replicates for each concentration, while the control seedlings were treated with water only. The same procedure was followed for seedlings treated with two concentrations 0.5 and 1 ml / liter of pesticides Changer 24%SC and super Hulk 11.8% SE (Table 1) at five replicates for each concentration, while the control seedlings were also treated with water only. Mortality rates for these treatments were calculated after 24, 48 and 72 hours of treatment. The percent reduction ratio was determined using to Abbot's formula (Abbott, 1925).

$$\text{Correct \%} = \frac{n \text{ in T in treatment}}{n \text{ in Co after treatment}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Where: n = Insect population, T = treated, Co = control

Statistical Analysis

Laboratory experiments were designed according to a completely randomized design

(CRD), Results were compared using the least significant difference (LSD) at 5% significance level. The statistical analysis was performed using GENSTAT software.

Table 1. Trade Name, Active Ingredient, and Chemical Group of Tested Bio and Chemical Pesticides

Trade name	Active ingredient	Chemical group
Tondexir 80% EC	Red Pepper and Garlic Extract	Botanical pesticides
Palizin 65%EC	Organic Saponins	Botanical pesticides
Changer 24%SC	Chlorfenapyr	Pyrroles
Super Hulk 11.8 EC	Hexythiazox +Abamectin	Growth inhibitor + Avermectin

Results

The table 2 showing the evaluates the efficacy of Tondexir and Palizin at two concentrations (1 ml and 2 ml) over three time periods (24, 48, and 72 h). Efficacy generally increased over time, reaching its highest rates at 72 h (75.83% overall). The higher concentrations (2 ml) performed consistently better than the lower

concentrations (1 mL), with mean rates of 63.61% and 55.00%, respectively. Tondexir showed slightly higher overall efficacy (61.94%) than Palizin (56.66%). Statistical analysis (LSD) confirmed that the differences between treatments, concentrations, and time periods, as well as their interactions, were significant at the 0.05 level.

Table 2. Evaluation of the Efficacy of Different Concentrations of Tondexir and Palizin against Adult Cotton Thrips, *T. tabaci*

Treatments	Concentration/ml		Time period / hours			Treatment rate
			24	48	72	
Tondexir 80% EC	1		38.33	65.00	76.67	61.94
	2		48.33	66.67	76.67	
Palizin 65%EC	1		30.00	53.33	66.67	56.66
	2		43.33	63.33	83.33	
Time period rate			40.00	62.08	75.83	
Concentration rate	1	2				
	55.00	63.61				
L.S. D			Treatment	Concentration	Period	Interaction
			4.021	4.021	9.5801	19.159
Level of Significance			0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05

The table 3 showing evaluates the efficacy of two pesticides, Changer 24% SC and Super Hulk 11.8% EC, at two concentrations (0.5 ml and 1 ml) over three time periods (24, 48, and 72 h). Super Hulk 11.8% EC consistently achieved the highest efficacy, reaching 100% mortality at both concentrations by 48 h, while Changer 24% SC demonstrated moderate efficacy, improving over time and concentration, with a maximum of 78.33% at 1 ml after 72 h. Overall, efficacy

increased across time periods, with rates of 62.91%, 72.08%, and 79.58% at 24, 48, and 72 h, respectively. Higher concentrations (1 ml) were more effective, with an average efficacy of 76.11% compared to 66.94% for 0.5 ml. Statistical analysis (LSD) confirmed that there were statistically significant differences in treatment, concentration, time period, and their interactions at the 0.05 level.

Table 3. Evaluation of the Efficacy of Different Concentrations of Changer 24%SC and Super Hulk 11.8% EC against Adult Cotton Thrips *T. tabaci*

Treatments	Concentration/ml		Time period / hours			Treatment rate
			24	48	72	
Changer 24%SC	0.5		26.67	35.00	40.00	45.00
	1		36.67	53.33	78.33	
Super Hulk 11.8 % EC	0.5		88.33	100.00	100.00	98.05
	1		100.00	100.00	100.00	
Time period rate			62.91	72.08	79.58	
Concentration rate	0.5	1				
	76.11	66.94				
L.S. D			Treatment	Concentration	Period	Interaction
			8.315	8.315	10.633	23.265
Level of Significance			0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05

Discussion

The results of this study indicated that the *T. tabaci* population was significantly impacted 72 hours after exposure to the Palizin which caused an 83.33% mortality after 72 hours, demonstrating that this insecticide acts more rapidly than Tondexir 80% EC. Palizin was found to be highly effective against cotton thrip on cucumber (Mahmoudi & Mohammadi, 2024). Another study also showed that Palizin caused 39.96% mortality in citrus blackfly 72 hours after application (Gholamzadeh-Chitgar & Pourmoradi, 2017). The lower efficacy of botanical insecticides compared to chemical insecticides in this study is consistent with the results of previous research. The results of this study showed that the increased mortality rate of adult of *T. tabaci* occurred with increasing concentrations and duration of application of Tondexir and Palizin. Although Tondexir and Palizin do not have the same lethal effects as chemical insecticides, these plant extracts, especially Palizin, showed relatively good efficacy in controlling *T. tabaci*. Capsaicin, the active ingredient in red pepper, has been shown to be toxic and have anti-feedant effects on arthropods, which may explain the lethal effects of Tondexir (Li et al., 2019). Kaberi and Amiri-Bishelli (2012) found that Palizin creates a physical and chemical barrier against insect pests, demonstrating great potential for effective pest control in various agricultural crops. The lethal effects of Palizin have been attributed to

its ability to damage the pest's exoskeleton and interfere with its respiratory system, causing leakage of vital fluids and leading to death (Torani et al., 2020).

The results of this study indicated that the *T. tabaci* population was significantly impacted 48 and 72 hours after exposure to the Super Hulk 11.8 % EC which caused an 100.00% mortality at both 48 and 72 hours at concentration 0.5 and 1 ml respectively, demonstrating that this insecticide acts more rapidly than Changer 24%SC. Mannan et al. (2021) demonstrated that abamectin at 13% w/w exhibited moderate efficacy, achieving 53.81% and 56.66% control of *T. tabaci* 7 days after the first and second spray, respectively, indicating a reasonably successful outcome. Similarly, Jarwa et al. (2014) found that Novastar 56 EC (containing 6% bifenthrin and 0.07% abamectin) effectively reduced thrips population, achieving a control rate of 66.48%.

Mohamed (2022) reported that abamectin showed significant toxicity against thrips. Building on these findings, the results of this study indicated that the Super Hulk 11.8 % EC, a combination (Hexythiazox and Abamectin), demonstrated enhanced toxicity against *T. tabaci*. This is aligning with the findings of Mohamed and Ibrahim (2022), who reported that the combination of Thiamethoxam and Abamectin was more effective against *T. tabaci* than using Thiamethoxam or Abamectin individually. Similarly, Hassanin (2023) indicated that the effectiveness of the insecticide Vertimec 1.8%

EC (Abamectin + Peppermint Oil) increased progressively, reaching its highest effectiveness after 10 days of application, with control efficiency against *T. tabaci* recorded at 81.55% and 79.11%, respectively. Additionally, a study by Wakil et al. (2024) demonstrated that the combined application of entomopathogenic fungi (EPF) with abamectin resulted in complete mortality of both nymphs and adults of *Tetranychus urticae*.

Conclusion

The combined application of the chemical insecticide Super Hulk 11.8% EC, a combination containing (hexythiazox and abamectin), at concentrations of 0.5 and 1 ml, proved highly toxic to thrips caused significant mortality in adult cotton thrips. Integrated use of insecticides can enhance cotton thrips control while reducing the risk of insecticides resistance and environmental pollution. Bioinsecticides such as Palizin and Tondexir, standalone treatments showed potential for controlling cotton thrips and could serve as alternatives to chemical insecticides. Field studies are recommended to further confirm and validate the findings of this study.

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